

Teachers as Being the Crucial Source of Education

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Abstract

This study deals with a topic entitled "Teachers as Being the Essential Source of Education". The theme of the topic is truly humble, yet from the point of view of the people intricate in the business of teaching and learning, it seems very complicated. The research comprises introduction, aim of the topic, education and culture, teaching and learning and the dangers of overconfidence followed by certain items presented as subtitles. The paper ends with a conclusion which sums up the essential findings of the paper.

1. Introduction

It has been agreed that teachers are the prime source of education. They are considered the backbone of role models to their students specially children. Teachers with different specializations offer guidance and dedication and give young people the power of education. Because of teachers countries prosper and flourish socially and economically and become able to survive and develop.

Teachers usually tell a story or portray an important character on the stage by dialogue action that named as an actor. This article is about the nature of the work of teachers and actors and the interchangeability of their social roles in the process of teaching and learning.

Teaching and learning are the most important activities practiced through various stages of education. People may ask what is education, what is it about, what does it comprise, and how does it function? Education is the process of making teaching and learning at all social levels easy. Through education learners, students, scholars, and even professors of different specializations acquire knowledge, skills, values, beliefs and habits. Education is considered one of the most powerful things in life. It allows people of different social ranks to find the valuable meaning behind everything and helps improve lives to a great extent in a massive way.

2- Aim

The aim of this paper can be divided into three parts. The first part is to prove that teachers and actors have a lot in common.

The second part of the aim is to shed light on the importance of the vital role of both teachers and actors in making the wheel of the process of teaching and learning move forward successfully.

The third part of the aim is to focus on the bad effects and dangers caused by the anti-social behavior of some educated people who always feel superior and overconfident in life.

3- Education and culture

The focal determination of education is to bring civilization into the society and if education is unsuccessful in resounding about improvement and well-being then it is regarded to be of no efficacy. Education, according to [Kapur](#), Radhika (2018: 3), is considered to be the most powerful instrument in bringing about changes within an individual. Teachers and actors participate in making the machine of education keep working. The outcome of sound education systems is culture. Culture is known as the way of life, customs, traditions and beliefs of a particular group of people at a particular time.

Any nation, any society, any community, any tribe or entity has a culture to be proud of. A nation with poor culture cannot survive and develop. Any nation, rich or poor, can be identified by its culture. Culture is the identity of a nation. It is its everlasting history which outlives all other social activities. Educational institutions, educators, and educational materials count among the most effective agents of cultural development, change, (Rossi, P.; 2009: 32).

But, unfortunately, everything in our world is subject to decay due to dangers caused by wars, earthquakes, fire, and diseases. When these unfortunate calamities and disasters happen they destroy almost everything including

education systems and cultures. Destroyed buildings and properties can be rebuilt and lost belongings can be, by course of time, restored, but lost civilizations and culture of a nation can never be restored.

Culture plays an important role in man's life. Awareness regarding various kinds of culture can help an individual in adjusting to the natural and social environment, developing an individual's personality, socialization of the individual, proper use of freedom, and understanding other cultures and proper meaning of liberality, (Kapur, Radhika (2018:5).

Cautious nations should, therefore, try their best not to expose their civilizations and culture to danger of any sort. This can be done by educating people and making them aware of these dangers and try to avoid them.

4- Teachers and actors

Teachers and actors, in their work, have differences and similarities. In life habits and behaviors they are different wherever they are, at home, in supermarkets, coffee shops or nightclubs etc. In the meantime they are alike in the nature of their profession.

A teacher provides people with knowledge by delivering lectures and an actor also provides his audiences knowledge by telling a story or portraying a famous character through action and dialogue. Consequently, both teachers and actors can be considered the source of knowledge and information, .

5- Settings

As far as settings are concerned, the teacher meets his students in a room called classroom. In this room students are seated to watch, listen and pay attention to what their teacher has to say.

This situation provides the opportunity for the students and their teacher to meet and get acquainted with each other and have mutual conversations and opinions regarding their study, (White, V.;1988: 21).

The actor meets his audiences in a place called theatre and he/she performs his/her part in the play on the stage by means of action and dialogue.

6- In The Classroom

Classroom culture involves the process of creating an environment where students and their teacher meet and get to know each other. In a classroom student are supposed to behave well during the lecture and cooperate with their teacher and create the proper atmosphere to make their teacher deliver the lecture smoothly and comfortably, (Walter, E.; 2008: 32). On the other hand a teacher should do whatever he/she can to make his/her students understand the subject in question. This can possibly be done by using all kinds of teaching methods and devices, such as a smart board and other electronic means.

But this is not enough. A teacher, most of the time, has to behave like an actor in the class in order to draw the attention of his/her students understand the idea he/she has in his/her mind, (Bynom, A. ; 2001: 56) .

A good teacher should not hesitate to imitate things during the lecture by using his/her voice or his/her hands, or by using body language just like an actor. In case students misbehave or get bored for one reason or another, a smart teacher must not be angry or disappointed, he/she must not hesitate to joke with his/her students and make them laugh just to restore their attention. It is necessary for a teacher to do that from time to time just to make sure that his/her students are awake.

7- On The stage

An actor, on the stage, has a script or a text to abide with during performance and by means of a dramatic action and dialogue he/she conveys the message to the audiences. No matter what the message is the audiences, at the end of the play, are supposed to end up with a moral lesson, (Best, J. W. & J. V. Kahn; 2006: 45).

Consequently, the classroom in any school and the stage in any theatre are in fact one source of spreading knowledge that enlightens the intellect and paves the way that leads man towards a better learning and a better life.

8- Overconfidence

Overconfidence in life refers to a biased and unjust way of appreciating and looking at a situation. When a person is overconfident he/she misjudges the values, opinions, and beliefs of other people.

Overconfidence can cause a person to experience difficulties and problems because he/she may not be ready to deal with a particular situation or may get into a dangerous situation that he/she is not equipped to handle. An overconfident person thinks that he/she is always right, that he/she is superior and other people inferior, Good,C.; Barr, A.& Douglas, E.; 1976: 14).

An overconfident person thinks that he is in rank above his/her colleagues. He/she could show his/her overconfidence by going on a long trip without enough money, without enough food and without a map and refusing to ask for directions if he/she gets lost along the way.

Overconfidence in education not only destroys the overconfident people but also destroys the scientific future of the whole nation.

9- Overconfident teachers in the class

An overconfident teacher who thinks he/she is highly educated and not in need of advice or help of any sort does not welcome opposite opinions which contradict his point of view. An overconfident teacher sometimes behaves sarcastically in his/her class when a student gives the wrong answer to a particular question. Such an overconfident teacher is rigid, harsh and cruel with his/her students. He/she does not treat students well and scorns them for no reason whatsoever and underestimate their abilities, (Patric, H.; 1971:56).

This bad behavior is wrong. Teachers should encourage their students especially smart students by respecting their opinions.

A good teacher should not be ashamed of him/herself when he/she makes a little mistake during the lecture. Teachers and professors of different specialization must remember that "to err is human". When a teacher makes a mistake during the lecture he/she must admit it, correct the mistake and apologize. Such a positive behavior of the teacher makes the student think highly of their teacher, (Bynom, A.; 2001: 12).

Unfortunately some overconfident teachers never admit making a mistake during a lecture or during a conversation and never accept or appreciate advice or directions from anybody. Professors, teachers, scholars, and students should never stop learning. They should always be ready to learn.

A prisoner once wrote on the wall of his cell in the prison the following:

"No man is your friend.
No man is your enemy.
Everyman is your teacher." (Glover, D. & D. Miller: 2007).

The above quotation means that no matter who you are, no matter whom you meet, friend or foe, you ought to learn something and let your enemy and your friend teach you something. The knowledge you keep tells people who you are. Some professors and teachers especially those who hold high academic degrees refrain from reading books and stop pursuing their study on the basis that they are highly educated and they are no longer in need of extra instructions.

Degree holders should always renew their knowledge, because what they have learned needs to be updated, (Celce, M.: 2001).

A person may work hard to keep his/her job to ensure a decent living, but not at the expense of knowledge and learning. Knowledge is more important than money because knowledge makes money.

10- Conclusion

Teachers are truly actors. Teachers and actors have a lot in common, they both teach people, but in their own way. A teacher, in a classroom, teaches his students how to read and write. Reading and writing is the corner stone of education.

Actors, on the other hand, teach people by telling a story or portraying a character through performance done on the stage. When people watch a play for example they get to know important things about a particular incident or a particular character which they did not know before. At the end of a comedy or a tragedy the audiences usually end up with a moral lesson.

Huge buildings, roads, and bridges are often exposed to dangers, such as wars, earthquakes and diseases. These dangers destroy almost everything including education and culture. The destroyed buildings and infrastructure of a country can, by course of time, be rebuilt and lost belongings can also be restored. The only thing which cannot be restored easily is lost knowledge and lost culture.

Thus, the government and the people should cooperate in order to avoid these dangers.

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